

Ruptured Pulmonary Hydatid Cyst with Hepatic Involvement: Diagnostic and Surgical Challenges

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Introduction

Hydatid disease, caused by *Echinococcus granulosus*, is a parasitic infection common in several temperate regions, including Romania. The hydatid cyst has a pathomorphologically layered structure, and cystic echinococcosis typically follows a slow, asymptomatic course. However, disruption of cyst integrity may result in severe, life-threatening complications. We report a complex case of a ruptured hydatid cyst with acute presentation and an initially uncertain diagnosis.

Case Presentation

A 51-year-old male presented to the emergency department with dyspnea, hemoptysis, and fatigue. Initial evaluation included chest computed tomography (CT), which suggested a left-sided pulmonary abscess associated with pneumonia. Microbiological investigations were negative for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* but positive for *Staphylococcus aureus*, leading to targeted antibiotic therapy. Initial imaging findings were interpreted in isolation, without correlation with potential extrapulmonary pathology, which contributed to diagnostic uncertainty. Despite treatment, the patient's condition deteriorated, with progressively rising inflammatory markers. Repeat imaging identified a left-sided hydropneumothorax. Clinical reassessment, combined with a history of recent exposure to domestic animals, raised suspicion of a ruptured, secondarily infected pulmonary hydatid cyst complicated by pyopneumothorax. The patient underwent surgical intervention via left lateral thoracotomy. Intraoperatively, purulent pleural effusion containing hydatid membrane fragments and generalized pachypleuritis were identified. Pleuropulmonary decortication, evacuation of the infected material, and management of the residual cavity were performed, achieving complete lung re-expansion. Follow-up abdominal CT revealed a subcapsular hydatid cyst in hepatic segment VII, along with a newly developed daughter cyst exhibiting wall disruption. Given the risk of further complications, urgent laparoscopic excision was performed, with an uneventful postoperative course.

Conclusion

This case highlights that hydatid disease may be overlooked if pulmonary findings are assessed in isolation, delaying recognition of disseminated involvement. Therefore, awareness of atypical presentations and a multidisciplinary approach are essential for timely diagnosis and appropriate surgical management.

Keywords

Hydatid cyst; cystic echinococcosis; ruptured pulmonary cyst